

Photolysis of Hexamethyldisilane

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Recently some papers have appeared on thermolysis of hexamethyldisilane at different temperatures¹⁻⁴. The results of photolysis of hexamethyldisilane under u.v. light is being reported here.

Hexamethyldisilane sealed under vacuum in silica tube was irradiated with u.v. light (mercury lamp, 236 m μ) for 170 hr. The tube was opened to a conventional glass vacuum line and volatile products separated. The G.L.C., I.R. and N.M.R. analysis of the compound irradiated resolved the presence of following compounds in the percentage yield taken on the basis of hexamethyldisilane consumed.

- (1) Me₃SiH 27% ; (2) Me₃Si-CH₂-SiMe₂H 7% ; (3) Me₃Si-CH₂-SiMe₃ 3.5% ;
 (4) High boiling fraction and solid 52%.

Since there are conflicting reports about the formation of product 2 in thermolytic reactions^{3,4}, it was isolated from the mixture of products formed in the present investigations by preparative G.L.C. and its structure was elucidated with the help of I.R., N.M.R. and mass spectral studies. Again, the presence of this compound was detected in most of the reactions of hexamethyldisilane and alkyl halides under u.v. light⁵

The high boiling material gave Si-CH₂-Si absorption at 1040-1050 cm⁻¹ and indicates the presence of Me₃Si, Me₂Si and CH₂ groups in the N.M.R. spectrum. The formation of the compounds may be explained on the basis of the following mechanism :

and

Under these conditions Me₃Si H and Me₃Si-CH₂-Si Me₂H may undergo further reactions to yield the high molecular weight material.

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